

Extraction of rhodium(III) from malonate media using 4-(4-ethylbenzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT)

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Abstract : Extraction of rhodium(III) with 4-(4-ethylbenzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT) from malonate media is described. Extraction was found quantitative with 0.1 *M* EBIMTT in chloroform in the pH range 1–2. From organic phase of EBIMTT, rhodium(III) was stripped out with 1 *M* HCl and determined spectrophotometrically with standard stannous chloride method. Effect of various parameters such as reagent concentration, equilibration period, effect of various diluents and divers ions on the extraction of rhodium(III) was also studied. The method affords binary separation of rhodium(III) from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II), and is applicable to the analysis of synthetic mixtures, alloys and spent catalysts. The method is fast, accurate and precise.

Keywords : Rhodium(III), liquid-liquid extraction, EBIMTT, malonate media.

Introduction

Rhodium is present at about 0.001 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in the earth's crust. Rhodium metal is known for its stability in corrosive environments, physical beauty and unique physical and chemical properties. Rhodium is now widely used in combination with platinum, in addition to or instead of palladium for automobile-exhaust emission control catalyst¹.

The wide application of the rhodium in the industrial process next to their extremely scarcity due to their natural abundance and the complexity of the process used for its extraction and refining, therefore it is of paramount importance in the development of separation method to recover these metals to meet the future demand.

Solvent extraction is currently one of the most important separation processes in industry in the processing of platinum group metals². This technology has the ability to selectively extract one element from a mixture of elements under certain pH conditions, enabling the purification of a metal or separation of different metals from one another. Different types of extractants are available, with different selectivities for specific metals.

Solvent extraction separation technique is preferred because of its several major advantages, such as (i) simple to operate; (ii) high pre-concentration factor; (iii) rapid phase separation; and (iv) the ability to combine with different detection techniques. After preconcentration with solvent extraction Rh^{III} was determined spectrophotometrically with stannous chloride method^{3–6}.

Rhodium being a soft acid, can be selectively extracted with soft donor base extractants containing 'N' or 'S' atoms. Based upon this presumption, several extractants, namely, alkylated 8-hydroxyquinoline⁷, Kelex 100^{8,9}, Cyanex 921¹⁰, TBP¹¹, *N,N*-dialkyl-*N'*-benzoylthioureas¹², dioctyl sulphides¹³, trialkylphosphinesulphide¹⁴ have been studied or used for the extraction of rhodium(III). These methods suffer due to the drawbacks such as operating conditions, longer equilibration time, synthesis of extractant, critical pH range etc.

Schiff bases have emerged as powerful extractants for many elements. The use of EBIMTT and MBIMTT in the extraction of noble metals has been described in our earlier published research results^{15–18}. The advantages of the proposed method over the reported one from this labo-

ratory for rhodium(III) extraction from hydrochloric acid media using MBIMTT¹⁵ are (1) aquo-chloro complexes of rhodium(III) converted into more stable rhodium malonate complexes, which undergo aquation to a lesser extent, making them more easily extracted; (2) the method is little ecofriendly, as the extraction carried from weak organic acid; (3) lower reagent concentration is required; and (4) many metal ions do not interfere. This article deals with the rapid and quantitative extraction of rhodium(III) from malonic acid at pH 2.0 with 0.1 mol/L of EBIMTT in chloroform as rapid and quantitative. The proposed method offers extraction separation and determination of rhodium(III) from alloys, catalysts, and also from associated elements.

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-(4-ethylbenzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT) :

The equimolar concentration of 3-ethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole¹⁹ and 0.02 mole of ethylbenzaldehyde in 50 ml alcohol containing 3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 3–4 h. The product obtained was separated and recrystallized from hot ethanol as light yellow compound (m.p. 144 °C), ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 2.59 (5H, s, -C₂H₅), 7.2 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 7.6 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 8.1 (1H, s, -CH), 3.0 (1H, s, -SH). Mass *m/e* : 246 (100.0%) (M⁺).

Chemicals :

EBIMTT (0.1 M) was used as an extractant; its solution was prepared in chloroform. A stock solution of Rh^{III} was prepared by dissolving 1 g of rhodium trichloride trihydrate (RhCl₃·3H₂O) in dilute analytical reagent grade hydrochloric acid (1 M) diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and standardized gravimetrically²⁰. A working solution of 200 µg ml⁻¹ of Rh^{III} was prepared by diluting the stock solution with distilled water. Other standard solutions of different metal ions used to study the effect of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of respective salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled water was invariably used throughout the measurements.

Instruments :

A Jasco V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with 1 cm

quartz cells was used for absorbance measurement, pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter model LI-120 (±0.01).

General procedure :

An aqueous solution containing 200 µg Rh^{III} mixed with a sufficient quantity of sodium malonate (0.2 g) in a total volume of 25 ml of the solution. Then the pH of the solution was adjusted to 1.0 using dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. The solution was transferred into a 125 ml separating funnel and shaken with 10 ml of 0.1 M EBIMTT in chloroform for just 30 s. After equilibration, the mixture was allowed to separate and the metal was stripped from the organic phase with two 10 ml portions of 1 M hydrochloric acid solution. The extracts were evaporated to moist dryness. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of 1 M hydrochloric acid and transferred into 50 ml volumetric flask, 10 ml of 20% potassium iodide was added, the solution was mixed well and heated for 15 min in boiling water bath. To the cooled solution, 10 ml of 10% stannous chloride solution was added and diluted with distilled water containing 1 M hydrochloric acid in final concentration. Place the unstopper flask in boiling water bath for 2 min. The solution was cooled and the absorbance of reddish brown solution was measured at 460 nm against a reagent blank²¹.

Results and discussion

Rhodium(III) reacts with extractant and forms 1 : 1 metal-ligand complex. The complex has maximum absorption at 460 nm. The molar absorptivity (1.7 × 10⁴ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and Sandell's sensitivity (0.065 µg cm⁻²) of the complex suggests that trace and ultra trace level quantities of rhodium can be quantified with required accuracy and precision. The influence of various factors like pH, reagent concentration, choice of solvent and effect of foreign ions on the extraction efficiency of rhodium(III) has been studied for optimizing the conditions for the selective and rapid extraction at trace level quantities.

Effect of acidity :

The extraction of Rh^{III} was carried out from different organic acids such as sodium salts of malonic acid, salicylic acid, tartaric acid, acetic acid, ascorbic acid. Quantitative results were obtained in the sodium malonate medium (0.03 M) in the pH range 1–2. While in tartaric

acid, salicylic acid, ascorbic acid, acetic acid very less extraction was found. Hence the sodium salt of malonic acid was used for further studies (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Extraction behaviour of rhodium(III) as a function of pH from sodium malonate, ascorbate and tartarate media with 0.1 M EBIMTT in chloroform.

Effect of concentration of extractant (EBIMTT) :

The extraction of Rh^{III} was carried out with varying concentration of EBIMTT at constant sodium malonate concentration. The concentration was varied from 0.01–0.2 M of extractant in chloroform. The quantitative extraction of 200 µg of Rh^{III} was observed at 0.06–0.15 M

of extractant. In present work we have used 0.1 M of extractant to ensure complete extraction of Rh^{III}.

Effect of time on extraction :

The effect of time was observed on the system for a period of 5 s to 30 min (hand shaking) the extraction was found quantitative over the periods longer than 10 s. But to ensure the complete extraction of Rh^{III} 1 min equilibration time was recommended. However, a prolonged shaking period doesn't have any adverse effect on the extraction.

Effect of stripping agents :

Rh^{III} was stripped with different stripping agents such as mineral acids, bases, and salts after its extraction. The stripping of Rh^{III} was quantitative with 1 M hydrochloric acid. The stripping was found to be incomplete with ammonia (60%), and sodium chloride (40%), with nitric acid (20%), whereas Rh^{III} was not stripped with sulphuric acid, sodium hydroxide and water.

Effect of diverse ions :

Rh^{III} was extracted in the presence of a large number of several foreign cations and anions (Table 1). The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ions cause ±2% error in recovery of Rh^{III}. The results showed that

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions added

Ions added	Added as	Tolerance limit (mg)	Ions added	Added as	Tolerance limit (mg)
Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .5H ₂ O	10	Tartarate	C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	100
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂	20	Citrate	C ₆ H ₈ O ₇ .H ₂ O	100
Cd ^{II}	CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	15	Fluoride	NaF	100
Ce ^{IV}	Ce(SO ₄) ₂	10	Acetate	CH ₃ COONa	100
Co ^{II}	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	10	Au ^{III}	HAuCl ₄ .4H ₂ O	0.5
Cr ^{III}	CrCl ₃	15	Sulphate	Na ₂ SO ₄	100
Cu ^{II}	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	5	Mo ^{VI}	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .2H ₂ O	20
Fe ^{III}	NH ₄ Fe(SO ₄) ₂ .12H ₂ O	15	Nitrate	KNO ₃	100
Fe ^{II}	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	15	Oxalate	(COOH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	100
Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	15	Bromide	KBr	100
Mn ^{II}	MnCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	10	Ru ^{III}	RuCl ₃ .xH ₂ O	0.5
Ni ^{II}	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5	Pd ^{II}	PdCl ₂ .xH ₂ O	20
Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	15	Pt ^{II}	H ₂ PtCl ₆	0.5
Se ^{IV}	SeO ₂	15	Chloride	NaCl	100
Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	20	Succinate	Succinic acid	20
Te ^{IV}	Na ₂ TeO ₃	5	U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	10
Th ^{IV}	Th(NO ₃) ₄ .6H ₂ O	10	Iodide	KI	100
Zn ^{II}	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	15	Malonate	Malonic acid	20
Ti ^{IV}	K ₂ TiF ₆ .H ₂ O	10	EDTA	EDTA (Disodium salt)	100

in the extraction and determination $200 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the Rh^{III} , these ions have no significant effect. The reproducibility of Rh^{III} extraction investigated from six replicate measurements.

Applications :

Binary separation of Rh^{III} from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) :

The method allowed separation and determination of Rh^{III} from a binary mixture containing either iron(III) cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II). In a typical experiment, solution containing $200 \mu\text{g}$ of Rh^{III} was taken and known amounts of other metals were added. The separation of Rh^{III} from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) was accomplished with 0.1 mol/dm^3 EBIMTT in chloroform at 1 mol/dm^3 hydrochloric acid. Rh^{III} was estimated spectrophotometrically by stannous chloride method. The recovery of Rh^{III} and that added ions was 99.5% and results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis of synthetic mixture

Composition	Rhodium found (μg)	Recovery ^a (%)	R.S.D. (%)
Rh(200) + Pd(500) + Ru(200)	99.9	99.5	0.06
Rh(200) + Pd(500) + Au(200)	99.7	99.4	0.07
Rh(200) + Pt(500) + Au(200)	99.7	99.4	0.07
Rh(200) + Pt(500) + Pd(200) + Au(200)	99.6	99.5	0.06

Table 3. Binary separation of rhodium(III) from base metals

Composition of metal	Average % recovery Rh^{III}	R.S.D. (%)	Average recovery added metal ions	R.S.D. (%)
Rh^{III} , 200; Fe^{III} , 15000	99.8	0.19	99.2	0.24
Rh^{III} , 200; Co^{II} , 10000	99.2	0.20	99.4	0.23
Rh^{III} , 200; Cu^{II} , 5000	99.4	0.23	99.5	0.22
Rh^{III} , 200; Ni^{II} , 5000	99.0	0.22	99.4	0.20

Table 4. Analysis of synthetic mixtures corresponding to alloy

Alloy	Composition (%)	Rhodium taken (μg)	Rhodium found (μg)	Recovery ^a (%)	R.S.D. (%)
Palladium-rhodium alloy	Pd, 90; Rh, 10	90	89.8	99.7	0.2
Jewelry alloy	Ru, 4; Pd, 95; Rh, 1	50	49	99	0.4
Osmiridium alloy	Ru, 8; Os, 32; Ir, 45; Pt, 10; Rh, 11; Au 1	50	49.8	99.7	0.2

Analysis of synthetic mixtures :

The separation of Rh^{III} from other platinum group metals i.e. platinum, palladium and gold was carried out by taking advantage of differences in their optimum extraction and stripping conditions. The proposed method was successfully used in the determination of Rh^{III} different synthetic mixtures (Table 3). A solution containing $200 \mu\text{g}$ of Rh^{III} was taken and known amount of other metals were added. Under the optimum extraction conditions of Rh^{III} , there is a quantitative extraction of Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Ru^{III} and Au^{III} . But the co-extracted metal ions cannot be back-stripped by 1 M hydrochloric acid solution. Thus, the reagent (EBIMTT) is made selective towards Rh^{III} by taking an advantage of the stripping agent used.

Analysis of alloys :

To ascertain the selectivity of the reagent, the proposed method was successfully used in the determination of Rh^{III} in alloys. The synthetic mixtures were prepared corresponding to the composition of alloy. The results of the analysis are reported in Table 4. The average recovery of rhodium(III) was 99.5%.

Conclusion :

The present work points out that the synthesized extractant shows a good potential for the extraction of rhodium(III) from organic acid media. 4-(4-Ethylbenzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT) is able to effectively extract Rh^{III} from organic acid media. The extraction time is short and the extractant presents a good loading capacity and reusable. The proposed method is used for rapid and selective separation of Rh^{III} from associated ions in their binary mixtures, synthetic mixtures and alloys.

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